

Please answer the following questions regarding your **musical experience**.

1. Have you studied music?

- I have never studied music formally or informally
- I received informal music education (e.g. from a friend...) or I am self-taught
- I received formal music education (e.g. private music tuition, music school)

1.1 **If you have** studied music, for how long? _____ years

2. Do you play a musical instrument?

- I play no musical instrument
- I play one musical instrument
- I play more than one musical instrument

2.1 **If you play one or more musical instruments**, how would you rate your skills?
(consider your best instrument if you play more than one)

bad

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 good

3. Have you ever composed original music?

- I have never composed original music
- I have composed original music once or twice
- I have composed original music more than a few times

3.1 How confident are you in your ability to compose original music?

not at all

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 a lot